

Computational Study on Effect of Transition Metal (Mn and Fe) Doping on Structural, Electronic and Magnetic Properties of Hexagonal-Tungsten Trioxide (Hex-WO₃)

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Abstract

Over a decade it has been proved that electron doping and electron-phonon coupling play a vital role in controlling the wide band gap issues of some transition metal oxide within density functional theory. However, electron doping and electron-phonon mechanism alone cannot give an excellent description of the performance of photocatalytic in Hex-WO₃. In this study, we systematically investigate the effect of Single atom transition metal doping and introduce the Hubbard U correction. The electronic structure calculations on both Hex-WO₃ and A_xW_{1-x}O₃ (A=Mn, Fe) using density functional theory with Hubbard U (DFT+ U) were carried out. We have found that presence of $U=5.8\text{eV}$ for W in optimizing pure Hex-WO₃ produced a stable structure only with overestimation in crystal parameters, while the presence of Mn and Fe Impurities, as well as Hubbard correction ($U=4.6\text{eV}$ for Mn and $U=3.8\text{eV}$ for Fe) produced a stable structure with high anisotropic distortion in the lattice parameters and negative formation energies of about -1.992 eV and -1.651 eV for Mn and Fe doping respectively, while for the electronic properties, the present of U shows that Hex-WO₃ is direct wide gap material with a gap of about 2.7eV which is also an overestimation. But the presence of Mn and Fe impurities shrink the band gap and changes the band edge from nonmagnetic WO₃ to A_xW_{1-x}O₃ (A=Mn, and Fe) ferromagnetism with $2.7\ \mu\text{B}$ and antiferromagnetic with $1.815\ \mu\text{B}$ magnetic moment per defect in case of Mn and Fe doping respectively, indicating that Mn_xW_{1-x}O₃ can be a suitable material for magnetic water splitting.

Keywords: Hex-WO₃, DFT-GGA+ U , Doping, Electronic and Magnetic properties

1. Introduction

Transitional Metal oxide are one of the most fascinating classes of material which has A variety of electronic, magnetic and structural properties Rao, (1989). In recent years, transitional Metal oxides have been studied for different technological applications such as Nano and microelectronics He, and Antonelli, (2002)., information technology Sawa, (2008), military technology Rao, M. C. (2013) and photoelectrochemical (PEC) water splitting Kalanur, S. S., Yoo, Eom, and Seo, (2018). Among transitional metals oxide, Tungsten trioxide (WO₃) has been

discovered to be an excellent candidate in PEC Lee et al.(2000), Reich et al., (2000), Yamazoe et al., (2003) and Xue et al.,(2011). WO₃ has good conductivity, it's non-toxic, low cost and it is the most widely used in Electrochromic materials Deb et al., (1992).

The WO₃ is produced by treating the tungsten with alkaline. Hence, WO₃ has the highest melting point among all metals at ,410°C (6,170°F), with high electric conductivity and it's found naturally on earth, which can exclusively be combined with other elements in chemical compounds. Chemically tungsten oxide is insoluble in water and acid, but dissolves in an alkaline solution Cotton et al, (1999); Rollinson (2015). WO₃ is recognized as an important photocatalytic material due to its stability in acidic Condition and also shears a similarity in physiochemical properties with TiO₂ Santato et al., (2001), the compound is also a good candidate in electro-chromic, photo-chromic and gas sensing application He and Yao (2006).

Hence tungsten oxide has an n-type semiconductor with an indirect band gap of 2.6eV and a direct band gap of 4.0eV Likalter (2002). It has various phases of crystallograph, such as monoclinic, cubic, triclinic, hexagonal, tetragonal and orthorhombic Ramana (2006). WO₃N-type semiconductor properties Makes it a key material which is still under study.

Tungsten oxides have been recently discovered to exhibit a fascinating structural behavior, as the magnetic metal is doped with a bulk semiconductor tungstate. Altering the band gap of a compound, by introducing impurities to the compound to either increase or reduce the band gap of the material. Density functional theory (DFT) can be used to determine either the increase or decrease of the gap of the doped material. The common method of improving the performance of the material is by the addition of dopant.

WO₃'s limitation is its wide band gap which needs to be addressed, to improve the performance of the material for better optoelectronic and microelectronics devices applications. Therefore, doping with impurities is being introduced, to reduce the band gap and especially to investigate the effect of doping WO₃ with Fe and Mn on structural, electronic and magnetic properties using density functional theory (DFT) and density functional theory plus Hubbard's 'U' (DFT+U).

2. Computational Method

In this work, we use a plane-wave pseudopotential method within the density functional theory plus Hubbard (DFT+U) energy as implemented in the Quantum ESPRESSO code Giannozzi, et al (2017) to calculate the structural, electronic and Magnetic properties, of Hex A_xW_{1-x}O₃ (A= Mn, and Fe). The ion-electron interaction was accomplished by using ultrasoft Pseudopotential. The GGA-PBE was adopted for the exchange-correlation Perdew, Burke, and Ernzerh of (1996). A unit cell of Hex-WO₃ (W 2 and O 8) with experimental crystal parameters a=b=3.557Å, c=10.940Å and space group P6/mmc (194) was used for the computation Krüger, Koutiri and Bourgeois (2012). The electronic valence states of Mn (3d⁵ 4s²), Fe (3p⁶ 4s² 3d⁶), W (6s² 4f¹⁴ 5d⁴) and O(2s² 2p⁴) were employed. 530 eV was as the cutoff energy while 12 × 12 × 1 was used as k-

points mesh in the Brillouin zone to relax the unit cell while $8 \times 8 \times 1$ was used as k-points mesh to relax the doped system Hex $A_xW_{1-x}O_3$ ($A = \text{Mn}$, and Fe). In each case, the tolerance of 2.0×10^{-6} eV/Å for force per atom, a maximum displacement stress of 2.0×10^{-4} Å, and 0.01 GPa were achieved respectively. The U values ($U=5.8\text{eV}$ for W , $U=4.6\text{eV}$ for Mn and $U=3.8\text{eV}$ for Fe) were obtained using the linear response procedure implemented in Quantum ESPRESSO package. For the doping, we Modelled the system by creating a $2 \times 2 \times 1$ supercell (16 W atoms and 48 O atoms) and Substitute one W atom by Mn and Fe atom resulting in a 6.25% Mn and Fe concentration.

3. Result And Discussion

3.1 Structural Properties

3.1.1 Pure WO_3 (WO_3)

Figure 1 shows our optimized crystal structure of Hex- WO_3 , the structure remained stable only with increases in crystal parameters as $a = b = 3.831\text{Å}$ and $c = 11.110\text{Å}$. This indicates that our GGA+ U gives overestimated parameters as expected and reported for many transition metal Oxide any, (2013) and Archer, et al (2011). Similarly, ur calculated bond angles are found to be $\alpha = \beta = 84^\circ$, $\gamma = 126^\circ$, while bond lengths between one W and neighbor O ($W-O$) is found to be 1.93 ± 0.05 . These values were also overestimated when compare with the experimental values reported in Yuan et al (2011), but because of the significance of bond lengths in WO_3 structure, our obtained value indicates that the optimized structure is high energetic stability.

Figure 1: Optimized crystal structure of Pure Hex- WO_3

Figure 2(a) and (b) shows the doped systems. The doping is carried out on a $3 \times 3 \times 1$ supercell with 72 atoms, the substitution of one W with a single Mn and Fe atoms which is equivalent to 1.38% concentration. From the structure we have found That the introduction of the impurities causes an anisotropic distortion of the lattice parameters such that the b/c ratio is found to be smaller than that of the pure bulk value. This results in agreement with alkaline metal doped monoclinic WO_3 Tosoni et al (2014); Yang et al (2014), this distortion is believed to be the possible reason for shrinking the band gap of the material.

Figure 2: Optimized doped structure of (a) Fe doped Hex- WO_3 (b) Mn optimized crystal structure of Hex- WO_3

The structural distortions induced by defects are illustrated in Fig. 1. We observe that the O atoms surrounding a W vacancy (V_w) stay almost at their original positions, whereas nearby W atoms move towards an O vacancy (V_o), which reduces the W-W distance from 4.18Å (perfect structure) to 3.72Å. Several locations along the face and body diagonals of the WO_6 unit cell are tested for possible interstitial sites. We find that a W interstitial atom is stable only at the body center (W_i) with a W-O bond length of 2.08Å on average, which is significantly larger than in the perfect structure (1.93Å). An O interstitial atom can be located at the body center (O_i -1) or near a W atom (O_i -2). The O-O distance of 2.12Å in the O_i -1 case shows that there is no O-O bonding (1.21Å in an O_2 molecule), whereas in the O_i -2 case we obtain a W-O bond length of 1.92Å. An H interstitial atom either can bond to a single O atom with a distance of 0.98Å (H_i -1) or it can be located at the face center with O-H distances of 1.01Å and 1.67Å (H_i -2). Finally, an HO interstitial defect ($(HO)_i$) is found to behave similarly to H_i -2 with O-H distances of 1.02Å and 1.50Å.

3.1.2 Electronic Band Structure For Pure $WO_3 + U$

The DFT-GGS+U calculation for pure hexagonal WO_3+U structure, where Hubbard correction was added to WO_3 , to investigate the effect of U , to correct or remove the unwanted electrons contributions; The bands were selected along 7 symmetry points ($\Gamma \rightarrow M \rightarrow K \rightarrow G \rightarrow A \rightarrow L \rightarrow H$) and the band structure is plotted; therefore from the band structure Fig.3 below; it clearly shows that DFT Plus Hubbard gives a band gap of about 2.22eV with the Fermi level at zero. This result is close to the experimental value 2.24eV reported by Zhu, et al 2019.

Figure 3: Band Structure of Pure Hexagonal WO_3 with U

3.1.2 Magnetic Property of Pure $WO_3 + U$

However, for the calculation of density of state (DOS) and projected density of state (PDOS) of the pure WO_3+U , where there is a reduction of 5d W orbital in the conduction band as well as other peaks of the W orbital of 6p W and 5s W respectively, which is due to the addition of Hubbard correction which has effected the band gap shown in Fig 4 below.

Figure 4: Calculated (a) Total DOS and (b) PDOS of Pure WO_3+U

3.1.3 Electronic Band Structure for Mn doped- WO_3+U

The DFT-LDA optimized crystal cell constants of Mn Doped- WO_3 structure; the band structure was calculated consisting of 12 atoms with three elements (W_2 , Mn_1 and O_9) Fig 5 below, where a single atom of W was replaced with an atom of Mn. The bands were selected along 7 symmetry Points ($\Gamma \rightarrow M \rightarrow K \rightarrow G \rightarrow A \rightarrow L \rightarrow H$) and the band structure was plotted. The band gap shows the band edges along all the symmetry points Overlap across the Fermi level at zero, between the conduction and valence bands, which indicates that it is metallic in nature because of the dopant and the added Hubbard U parameters.

Figure 5: Band Structure of Mn Doped- WO_3+U

3.1.4 Magnetic Property of Mn Doped- WO_3+U

We calculated the density of state (DOS) and projected density of state (PDOS) of the Mn Doped- WO_3+U ; from the DOS of Fig. 6(a), there is a different contribution where the spin down has the highest peak in the valence band. And Figure 6(b) PDOS graph there are almost equal contributions of both spin up and spin down of 2s O orbital, 3p Mn spin up and spin down as well as 5s W spin up and spin down. However 5d W spin up has the highest peak contribution in the conduction band, with also contribution along the Fermi level of 4s Mn spin up and spin down respectively. Therefore, it indicates it's anti-ferromagnetic.

(a)

(b)
Figure 6: Calculated (a) Total DOS and (b) PDOS of Mn Doped- WO_3+U

3.2.5 Electronic Band Structure for Fe Doped- WO_3+U

The DFT-LDA optimized crystal cell constants of Fe Doped- WO_3+U structure; the band structure was calculated. The bands were selected along 7 symmetry points ($\Gamma \rightarrow M \rightarrow K \rightarrow G \rightarrow A \rightarrow L \rightarrow H$) and the band structure was plotted shown in Fig 7. There was overlapping of the band edges along the symmetry points, when the Fermi level is zero. Indicating that it's a metallic material even after when Hubbard correction was added to the Fe doped- WO_3 .

Figure 7: Band Structure of Fe Doped- WO_3+U

3.1.5 Magnetic Property of Fe Doped- WO_3+U

We calculated the density of state (DOS) and projected density of state (PDOS) of the Fe Doped- WO_3+U , where spin polarization was utilized and From the Fig. 8(a) DOS graph the spin down has the highest contribution which is in the valence band. And for Figure 4.17(b) PDOS graph, which has equal and highest contributions of 2s O spin up and 2s O spin down and 4p Fe spin up and 4p Fe spin down both in the valence band, However, also 5s spin down and 3d Fe spin up. However, in the valence band there is 3d Fe for spin up and spin down has an equal contribution, similarly 5s W spin up and down and 6p W spin up and spin down respectively. But close to the Fermi level, there's contribution of 5d W spin down but 5d W spin up is higher, which is due to the addition of Hubbard correction. Therefore indicates that it is anti-ferromagnetic.

Figure 8: Calculated (a) Total DOS and (b) PDOS of Fe Doped- WO_3+U

Table 1: Showing the Gap type, Band gap (eV) and type of the material for the various compounds

Compounds	Band Gaps (Ev)	Type Of Materials	Gap Types
WO_3+U	2.25	Semiconductor	Wide
Mn doped- WO_3+U	---	Metallic	No gap
Fe doped- WO_3+U	---	Metallic	No gap

4. Magnetic Moments

It is due to the high density of state of the materials at the Fermi level that made it non-magnetic as the result of impurities added to the material and also the Hubbard U parameters. The total energy that was calculated decreases with increasing magnetic moment; hence further increase of magnetic moment makes the occupation state to be occupied. Hence, to destabilize the structure, it will require high energy. As the total energy of the pure WO_3 compound reduces, the magnetic moment of the WO_3+U decreases to $0.34\mu_B$. This is due to the addition of Hubbard parameter. However, when the total energy of doped WO_3 with Mn and Fe decreases their magnetic moment increases to $2.46\mu_B$ and $2.57\mu_B$ respectively. Also, for the Mn doped- WO_3+U magnetic decreases to $0.75\mu_B$ while the magnetic moment for Fe doped- WO_3+U is higher at $44\mu_B$.

Table 2: Showing the compounds, Total energy (Ry) and Magnetic Moment (μ_B)

Compounds	Total energy(Ry)	Magnetic moment(μ_B)
WO ₃ +U	-2589.09392467	0.34
Mn doped-WO ₃ +U	-2130.08272082	0.75
Fe doped-WO ₃ +U	-2172.54893744	6.44

Figure 9: Graph of Calculated Magnetic Moment

5. Conclusion

Doping of WO₃ with iron and manganese and the addition of Hubbard parameter was investigated using the Quantum ESPRESSO code within DFT and DFT+U within the local density approximation (PBE-LDA) to calculate the total energy and the following conclusions were obtained.

1. It was found that the structure for the pure WO₃ and doped WO₃ (with Mn and Fe) are stable with Hubbard addition
2. While the material for pure WO₃ is a semiconductor, then U was added to the pure WO₃ it further widens its band gap, due to the Hubbard correction that was added to the pure WO₃. However, both doped-WO₃ with Fe and Mn made the materials to become metallic in nature.
3. However, Fe and Mn doped WO₃ with the added Hubbard correction parameter, the Iron-doped WO₃ with Hubbard correction is discovered to be anti-ferromagnetic, while the Manganese-doped WO₃ is also anti-ferromagnetic.

The electronic characteristic of the compounds shows that (pure WO₃ and WO₃+U) may be useful for optoelectronics applications fields such as resistors, diodes, etc. While the other compounds (Fe doped-WO₃, Mn doped-WO₃, Fe doped-WO₃+U and Mn doped-WO₃+U) which are metal may be useful in making wires, equipment and gadgets such as (iron, television and fridge), capacitors, transducers etc.

References

- Rao, C. N. R. (1989). Transition metal oxides. *Annual Review of Physical Chemistry*, 40(1), 291-326.
- Sawa, A. (2008). Resistive switching in transition metal oxides. *Materials Today*, 11(6), 28-36.
- Rao, M. C. (2013). Structure and properties of WO₃ thin films for electrochromic device application. *J. Non-Oxide Glasses*, 5, 1-8.
- He, X., & Antonelli, D. (2002). Recent advances in synthesis and applications of transition metal containing mesoporous molecular sieves. *Angewandte Chemie International Edition*, 41(2), 214-229.
- Kalanur, S. S., Yoo, I. H., Eom, K., & Seo, H. (2018). Enhancement of photoelectrochemical water splitting response of WO₃ by Means of Bi doping. *Journal of catalysis*, 357, 127-137.
- Giannozzi, P., Andreussi, O., Brumme, T., Bunau, O., Nardelli, M. B., Calandra, M., ... & Baroni, S. (2017). Advanced capabilities for materials modelling with Quantum ESPRESSO. *Journal of Physics: Condensed Matter*, 29(46), 465901.
- Perdew, J. P., Burke, K., & Ernzerhof, M. (1996). Generalized gradient approximation made simple. *Physical Review Letters*, 77(18), 3865.
- Krüger, P., Koutiri, I., & Bourgeois, S. (2012). First-principles study of hexagonal tungsten trioxide: Nature of lattice distortions and effect of potassium doping. *Physical Review B*, 86(22), 224102.
- Lany, S. (2013). Band-structure calculations for the 3 d transition metal oxides in G W. *Physical Review B*, 87(8), 085112.
- Archer, T., Pemmaraju, C. D., Sanvito, S., Franchini, C. E. S. A. R. E., He, J., Filippetti, A. L. E. S. S. I. O., ... & Majumdar, P. (2011). Exchange interactions and magnetic phases of transition metal oxides: Benchmarking advanced ab initio methods. *Physical Review B*, 84(11), 115114.
- Yuan, H. J., Chen, Y. Q., Yu, F., Peng, Y. H., He, X. W., Zhao, D., & Tang, D. S. (2011). Hydrothermal synthesis and chromic properties of hexagonal WO₃ nanowires. *Chinese Physics B*, 20(3), 036103.
- Tosoni, S., Di Valentin, C., & Pacchioni, G. (2014). Effect of alkali metals interstitial doping on structural and electronic properties of WO₃. *The Journal of Physical Chemistry C*, 118(6), 3000-3006.
- Yang, C., Chen, J. F., Zeng, X., Cheng, D., & Cao, D. (2014). Design of the alkali-metal-doped WO₃ as a near-infrared shielding material for smart window. *Industrial & Engineering Chemistry Research*, 53(46), 17981-17988.
- Zhu, F., Ma, C., Gu, L., Chen, G., Zhang, J., Cong, S. & Zhang, X. (2019). Off-centered-symmetry-based band structure modulation of hexagonal WO₃. *Journal of Physics: Condensed Matter*, 31(35), 355501.